

Supplementary Information for “Real-space anisotropy of the superconducting gap in the charge-density wave material 2H-NbSe₂”

Antonio Sanna,¹ Camilla Pellegrini,² Eva Liebhaber,³ Kai Rosnagel,^{4,5} Katharina J. Franke,³ and E.K.U. Gross⁶

¹*Max-Planck Institut für Mikrostrukturre Physics, Weinberg 2, 06120 Halle, Germany*

²*Department of Physics and Geology, University of Perugia, Via Pascoli 33, 06123 Perugia, Italy*

³*Fachbereich Physik, Freie Universität Berlin, Arnimallee 14, 14195 Berlin, Germany*

⁴*Institut für Experimentelle und Angewandte Physik,*

Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, 24098 Kiel, Germany

⁵*Ruprecht-Haensel-Labor, Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, 22607 Hamburg, Germany*

⁶*Fritz Haber Center for Molecular Dynamics, Institute of Chemistry,*

The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem 91904, Israel

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SUPPLEMENTARY NOTES

Supplementary Note 1. Lattice dynamics in the CDW phase

Supplementary Figure 1 left shows the energy of bulk NbSe₂ calculated in the local density approximation as a function of the CDW distortion for different values of the electronic temperature (smearing width, τ). Unlike the physical temperature, which also affects vibrational occupation numbers [1], τ is an artifact introduced to improve convergence with respect to the Brillouin zone sampling. As discussed in Ref. 2, for electronic temperature $\tau > 0.3$ eV, the CDW instability in 2H-NbSe₂ is suppressed restoring the high-symmetry state.

Supplementary Figure 1. Left: Energy profile of the CDW lattice distortion in the 3x3 supercell for different values of the electronic smearing width (τ) indicated in meV. Right, top to bottom: Phonon density of states (black) and electron-phonon coupling spectral function $\alpha^2 F$ (red) in the CDW cell ($\tau=0.27$ eV), for the unstable symmetric structure ($\tau=0.27$ eV) and for the stabilized symmetric structure ($\tau=0.87$ eV). Dashed lines are the λ integration curves $2 \int_0^x \alpha^2 F(\omega) / \omega d\omega$.

In Supplementary Figure 1 right we compare the calculated phonon density of states and electron-phonon spectral function $\alpha^2 F$ in the CDW state and in the undistorted states with and without CDW instability (this last state is obtained by assuming $\tau = 0.82$ eV). As one can see, the CDW formation has small effects on the phonon DOS. The lattice reconstruction associated with the CDW stabilizes the soft phonon modes in the undistorted structure, which, however, have low spectral weight (the modes are highlighted by a black arrow in the central panel of Supplementary Figure 1 right). On the other hand, the CDW modulation has a huge impact on $\alpha^2 F$. In fact, removing the lattice instability resolves the divergence in $\alpha^2 F$, which is by definition inversely proportional to the phonon frequency [3, 4].

Compared to that in the CDW state, the phonon DOS of the system stabilized at high τ shows a stiffening of the phonons in the high-energy region (>25 meV) and, more importantly, in the lower end of the spectrum (≤ 10 meV). We also note that the artificial stabilization of the lattice in the Ω_1 cell produces a significantly different electron-phonon coupling ($\lambda \simeq 1$). These observations strongly indicate that using a smearing width larger than 300 meV leads to unphysical results and should thus be avoided.

Supplementary Note 2. SCDFT simulations and computational details

Density functional theory for superconductors (SCDFT) is an extension of conventional DFT for *ab initio* calculations of material-specific properties in the superconducting state. The theory includes the superconducting order parameter $\chi_{sc}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ as an additional density. The corresponding non-interacting Kohn-Sham (KS) system then reproduces, in principle exactly, both the normal density and the superconducting order parameter of the real system. In the so-called decoupling approximation (on which Eliashberg theory is also based), the KS system is fully determined

by solving the BCS-like gap equation:

$$\Delta_{s k} = -\mathcal{Z}_k \Delta_{s k} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k'} \mathcal{K}_{k,k'} \frac{\tanh\left(\frac{\beta}{2} E_{k'}\right)}{E_{k'}} \Delta_{s k'}, \quad (1)$$

where $E_k = \sqrt{\varepsilon_k^2 + |\Delta_{s k}|^2}$ are the KS excitation energies, defined in terms of the KS gap function $\Delta_{s k}$ and the KS eigenvalues measured from the Fermi energy, β is the inverse temperature, and k is a combined band (n) and momentum (\mathbf{k}) index. The kernel of the equation consists of a diagonal part, $\mathcal{Z}_k = \mathcal{Z}_k^{ph}$, and a nondiagonal part, $\mathcal{K}_{k,k'}$. \mathcal{Z}_k^{ph} plays the role of the renormalization function in the Eliashberg equations, whereas $\mathcal{K}_{k,k'} = \mathcal{K}_{k,k'}^c + \mathcal{K}_{k,k'}^{ph}$, which includes both Coulomb and phonon-mediated effects, is responsible for the binding of the electrons in Cooper pairs. Eq. (1) allows one to account for the full anisotropy of materials at a low computational cost. The accuracy of the method is bound by the quality of the available functionals. In this work we used the recently developed SPG functional that enables accurate calculations of experimental superconducting critical temperatures and gap functions ($\Delta_{n\mathbf{k}}$) [5].

For an adequate description of the superconducting anisotropy, the k sampling in Eq. (1) needs to be extremely accurate, so as to resolve the meV energy scale of the superconducting gap. For this reason we adopted a random sampling Metropolis algorithm, in which a large number of k -points (approximately $1.4 \cdot 10^6$) is generated and densely accumulated near the Fermi surface [6]. These points were used to compute the superconducting gap and the gap distribution function, and to visualize FS properties such as the electron-phonon coupling shown in Fig. 3 of the main paper (MP).

We implemented a transformation of the \mathbf{k} -resolved superconducting gap back into real space as:

$$\Delta(R) = \sum_{n\mathbf{k}} \Delta_{n\mathbf{k}} |\phi_{n\mathbf{k}}(R)|^2 \delta(\varepsilon_{n\mathbf{k}}), \quad (2)$$

where $\phi_{n\mathbf{k}}$ are the KS orbitals. The expression above was used to compute the real space images of the superconducting gap shown in Fig. 5MP.

The SCDFT kernels depend on the phononic features and on the normal-state electronic structure [5, 7]. These properties were calculated within KS [8] density functional theory [9] in the local density approximation [10], as implemented in the Quantum Espresso code [11]. We used norm-conserving pseudopotentials to treat atomic core states, while valence states were expanded in a plane-wave basis set up to an energy cutoff of 70 Ry. Phonons were computed in the linear response regime by means of density functional perturbation theory [12–14]. The dielectric function was evaluated in the random phase approximation in the static limit, neglecting, owing to the extreme computational cost, CDW and anisotropy effects. Electronic eigenvalues were computed on a dense $24 \times 24 \times 16$ grid, from which the energy at the random sampled points was obtained by Fourier interpolation. Phonons were computed on a $2 \times 2 \times 4$ \mathbf{q} -grid and $4 \times 4 \times 4$ \mathbf{k} -grid, using a smearing width for the electronic occupations of 0.27 eV. The electron-phonon matrix elements were then computed on a denser $8 \times 8 \times 8$ \mathbf{k} -grid and linearly interpolated to the random set. Grid convergence was assessed by computing the Eliashberg spectral function and checking that it was not significantly affected by decreasing or increasing the \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{k} sets. The most critical convergence parameter is the smearing width, which should be chosen large enough to ensure convergence of the BZ integration, yet sufficiently small not to affect the stability of the CDW.

Supplementary Note 3. Simulation of the differential conductance spectra

We calculated the differential conductance as the first derivative of the tunneling current with respect to the bias voltage between the tip and the sample. For the tunneling current we used the expression:

$$I(V, \mathcal{R}) = \int d\omega \rho_t(\omega - V/2) \rho_s(\omega + V/2, \mathcal{R}) [f(\omega - V/2) - f(\omega + V/2)], \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{R} denotes the position of the tip apex on the sample, f is the Fermi distribution function, ρ_t and ρ_s are, respectively, the densities of states of the tip and the sample. ρ_t was defined by [15]:

$$\rho_t(\omega) = N_{F,t} \Re \frac{|\omega|}{\sqrt{\omega^2 - \Delta_t^2(\omega)}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta_t(\omega)$ and $N_{F,t}$ are the complex gap function and the Fermi DOS of the tip material. Analogously, the density of states of the sample at the tip position was obtained as

$$\rho_s(\omega, \mathcal{R}) = \sum_{n\mathbf{k}} \Re \frac{|\omega|}{\sqrt{\omega^2 - \Delta_{n\mathbf{k}}^2(\omega)}} \delta(\varepsilon_{n\mathbf{k}}) P_{n\mathbf{k}}^{\mathcal{R}} \quad (5)$$

where $P_{n\mathbf{k}}^{\mathcal{R}} = \int_{\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R})} d\mathbf{r} |\phi_{n\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})|^2$ represents the probability of finding an electron with band index n and wave vector \mathbf{k} in a small volume \mathcal{V} around the tip. It should be noticed that, whereas in experiment the STM tip apex scans the sample surface, in simulations \mathcal{R} is taken within the crystal to scan the volume of the sample. $\Delta_{n\mathbf{k}}(\omega)$ is the frequency dependent complex gap function. Since the frequency dependence of the computed gap did not show significant variations with k , we chose it equal to that of the isotropic gap, i.e., we assumed $\Delta_{n\mathbf{k}}(\omega) = \Delta_{n\mathbf{k}}^F(\omega)$. By inserting this expression and the identity $1 = \int \delta(\Delta_{n\mathbf{k}} - \Delta) d\Delta$ into Eq. 5, we obtained

$$\rho_s(\omega, \mathcal{R}) = N_F \int d\Delta \Re \frac{|\omega|}{\sqrt{\omega^2 - \Delta^2 F^2(\omega)}} d^{\mathcal{R}}(\Delta), \quad (6)$$

where

$$d^{\mathcal{R}}(\Delta) = \frac{1}{N_F} \sum_{n\mathbf{k}} \delta(\Delta_{n\mathbf{k}} - \Delta) \delta(\varepsilon_{n\mathbf{k}}) P_{n\mathbf{k}}^{\mathcal{R}}, \quad (7)$$

is the local (real-space) projection of the distribution of gap values over the FS.

Supplementary Figure 2 shows a comparison between the simulated tunneling current and differential conductance with a superconducting tip (green) and a normal tip (orange). As one can see, the use of a superconducting tip is essential for resolving the gap anisotropy.

Supplementary Figure 2. Simulated tunneling current and differential conductance using a superconducting (Nb) tip (green) and a normal tip (orange).

Supplementary Note 4. Atomic-scale variations of the tunneling spectra

As explained in the main manuscript, the CDW is incommensurate to the atomic lattice. This incommensurability can be perceived from STM images, as shown in Supplementary Figure 3a (see also Fig. 1a main part). In addition to the atomic corrugation of the terminating Se layer, we observe periodic height variations which can be ascribed to the charge-density wave (CDW) ($a_{\text{CDW}} \approx 3.05 \times 3.05 a_{\text{lattice}}$) [16–18]. As the CDW is not exactly commensurate, its maxima shift with respect to the atomic lattice. The close-up image in Supplementary Figure 3b presents a region, where the CDW maxima coincide with hollow sites (between 3 Se atoms, *i.e.* hollow-centered, HC pattern). In Supplementary Figure 3c the CDW maxima are aligned with Se atoms (*i.e.* chalcogen-centered, CC pattern). The atomic lattice is overlaid in each close-up image as a guide to the eye.

Differential conductance spectra taken at different lateral positions (indicated by the stars in Supplementary Figure 3b,c) reveal some intensity variations of the superconducting gap distribution (Supplementary Figure 3d). We observe small variations on the atomic scale when comparing different atomic sites (compare dark and light spectra

taken on Se atoms and hollow sites, respectively, within the regions of the HC CDW phase (orange) and the CC CDW phase (blue)). Similar atomic-scale variations of the differential conductance signal at the coherence peaks have been observed by Guillamon et al. using normal-metal tips [19].

Intensity variations on the scale of the CDW (HC vs CC structure) can be identified by comparing the dark (bright) traces of each color. Additional positions with respect to the CDW phase are shown in Supplementary Figure 4. The precise positions on the maximum, minimum and local minimum of the CDW are indicated by colored stars in the topography. The bottom trace is the average of all six spectra and is used for the comparison with the simulations in Fig. 5a of the main part.

Supplementary Figure 3. (a) Constant-current image of a clean NbSe₂ surface (recorded with a set point of 10 mV, 100 pA; the scale bar is 2 nm). (b,c) Close-up views of the different regions indicated in (a) to illustrate the smooth evolution of the CDW with respect to the atomic lattice. In (b) the CDW maxima fall on a hollow site (hollow-centered, HC) while the CDW maxima coincide with a Se atom in (c) (chalcogen-centered, CC). The atomic lattice is partially overlaid with Se (Nb) atoms in bright (dark) green. (d) Differential conductance dI/dV spectra taken on the clean NbSe₂ surface at the positions indicated with the colored stars in (b,c) recorded in constant-height mode with a Nb tip (feedback was opened at the position of the bright blue spectrum for all traces shown at 5 mV, 250 pA and a modulation of $15 \mu V_{\text{rms}}$ was used).

Supplementary Note 5. Height-dependent tunneling spectra

Our calculations are based on a three-dimensional crystal structure with periodic boundary conditions. Hence, the tip is placed “within” the atomic layers and we cannot simulate the decay of the wavefunctions into vacuum. To check the influence of the decay of the wavefunctions into vacuum, we recorded dI/dV spectra at different tip heights above the maxima of the CC and HC CDW phase, respectively (Supplementary Figure 5). We observe small variations of the relative peak intensities at different tip heights. While the largest peak is reduced in intensity upon tip approach to the surface, the high-energy shoulders gain intensity. These variations may be explained by the different decay constants of the electronic states originating from different parts of the Fermi surface (*c.f.* Fig. 3c main part). While exhibiting rather small gap values in the $k_z = 0$ -plane of the Fermi surface, the K-arcs show increased gap values at large k_z . As they also have significant k_{\parallel} -character their contribution to the tunneling current is thus more strongly suppressed when increasing the tip-substrate distance.

As the experiments reveal the sensitivity to the wavefunction decay, we suggest that the differences between the simulations and the experimental tunneling spectra may be explained by the different tip position, i.e. “within” the plane vs. above the surface. Specifically, states with k_z -character contribute more strongly to the tunneling current than states with large k_{\parallel} -character.

Supplementary Figure 4. (a) Constant-current image of a clean NbSe₂ surface (recorded with a set point of 10 mV, 100 pA; the scale bar is 2 nm). (b) Differential conductance dI/dV spectra taken on the NbSe₂ surface at the positions indicated with the colored stars in (a) recorded in constant-height mode with a Nb tip (feedback was opened at the position of the medium blue spectrum for all traces shown at 5 mV, 250 pA and a modulation of $15 \mu V_{\text{rms}}$ was used). The black curve is the average between all six colored spectra and is used in Fig. 5a of the main part. Spectra offset for clarity.

Supplementary Figure 5. Differential conductance dI/dV spectra recorded at different tip-sample distance using a Pb tip (a) on the maximum of the CDW in the HC, and (b) on the maximum of the CC structure. Feedback was opened at 4 mV, 200 pA before adding an additional offset of 0 pm, ± 100 pm to the tip's z -position. A modulation of $15 \mu V_{\text{rms}}$ was used. The tip's lateral position is indicated in the inset topographies (constant-current mode with set point: 4 mV, 200 pA).

Supplementary Note 6. Superconducting gap structure in the vicinity of defects

To corroborate the interpretation of 2H-NbSe₂ as anisotropic superconductor, we investigate the differential conductance spectra around the BCS coherence peaks in the vicinity of a variety of atomic-scale defects. In Supplementary Figure 6 we present STM images of different defects on an otherwise clean NbSe₂ surface together with their corresponding differential conductance spectra. In Supplementary Figure 6a we detect a “dark” defect in the atomically resolved STM topography, which most probably originates from a Se vacancy in the terminating layer. The gap spectrum (Supplementary Figure 6d) at this site shows a relative reduction of the low-energy contributions to the gap, while the high-energy part is enhanced in intensity. This observation can be understood by our SCDFT calculations, which reveal stronger superconductivity at Nb sites compared to Se sites. The absence of a Se atom allows a better access to the Nb sites in the tunneling path.

Supplementary Figure 6b shows an (unknown, possibly H) adsorbate. The superconducting gap shape (Supplementary Figure 6e) looks almost identical to the bare surface though with a slight apparent shift of the higher-energy peak to even larger energies. This implies that tunneling into states with stronger electron-phonon coupling is enhanced. While we cannot assign particular bands, Fig. 3d in the main manuscript shows that states with finite k_z contribute to stronger electron-phonon coupling, i.e. to stronger superconductivity. As an adsorbate suppresses tunneling with k_{\parallel} and enhances it with larger k_z , the observations are in agreement with our calculations.

In Supplementary Figure 6c we present a Pb atom which was deposited on the clean surface from the Pb tip in a controlled manner. We present a series of dI/dV spectra on the center of the atom as well as in its close vicinity in

Supplementary Figure 6. (a) Constant-current image of a clean NbSe₂ surface including a Se defect (recorded with a set point of 10 mV, 100 pA). (b) Constant-current image of a NbSe₂ surface with an adsorbate (recorded with a set point of 4 mV, 200 pA). (c) Constant-current image of a NbSe₂ surface with a single Pb atom (recorded with a set point of 100 mV, 100 pA). The Pb atom was deposited from the Pb tip by a voltage pulse on a clean and defect free position on the surface. The scale bars in (a-c) are all 2 nm. (d-f) Differential conductance dI/dV spectra taken on the positions indicated with the colored stars in the corresponding topographies in (a-c), recorded in constant-height mode with a set point of 5 mV, 250 pA (d) and 4 mV, 200 pA (e,f) and a modulation of $15 \mu V_{\text{rms}}$. The Nb or Pb tip gaps are indicated by the gray area.

Supplementary Figure 6f. The variation of relative peak heights is again evidence for the convolution of the tunneling paths with the density of states in the substrate. Similar to the adsorbate in (b,e), an enhancement of intensity at stronger superconductivity is found on top of the atom.

Comparing the spectra recorded on these defects to the spectra recorded on the pristine substrate (Supplementary Figure 6d-f) we note that the defects can change the spectral weights observed by STM. This is a manifestation of the changes of the tunnel selectivity into different parts of the Fermi surface and hence, arises from the highly anisotropic nature of the superconducting order parameter of NbSe₂.

The modulations of the superconducting energy gap on and around defects (cf. Supplementary Figure 6) highlight the importance of very clean substrates for investigations of the intrinsic gap structure of 2H-NbSe₂ sample. A distribution of defects may perturb the band structure, and, hence, strongly affect the superconducting pairing strength. Additionally, tunneling into certain parts of the Fermi surface may be suppressed.

Supplementary Figure 7 shows a large scale topography ($50 \text{ nm} \times 50 \text{ nm}$) of the pristine NbSe₂ surface showing the low impurity concentration.

Supplementary Figure 7. Constant-current image of a pristine NbSe₂ surface (recorded with a set point of 100 mV, 50 pA) with a Pb tip.

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- [1] Bianco, R., Monacelli, L., Calandra, M., Mauri, F. & Errea, I. Weak dimensionality dependence and dominant role of ionic fluctuations in the charge-density-wave transition of NbSe₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125**, 106101 (2020).
 - [2] Calandra, M., Mazin, I. I. & Mauri, F. Effect of dimensionality on the charge-density wave in few-layer 2H-NbSe₂. *Phys. Rev. B* **80**, 241108(R) (2009).
 - [3] Allen, P. B. & Mitrović, B. *Theory of superconducting T_c*, Vol. 37 of *Solid state physics* (Academic Press, 1983).
 - [4] Flores-Livas, J. A. et al. A perspective on conventional high-temperature superconductors at high pressure: methods and materials. *Phys. Rep.* **856**, 1-78 (2020).
 - [5] Oliveira, L. N., Gross, E. K. U. & Kohn, W. Density-functional theory for superconductors. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **60**, 2430-2433 (1988).
 - [6] Marques, M. A. L. et al. Ab initio theory of superconductivity. II. Application to elemental metals. *Phys. Rev. B* **72**, 024546 (2005).
 - [7] Lüders, M. et al. Ab initio theory of superconductivity. I. Density functional formalism and approximate functionals. *Phys. Rev. B* **72**, 024545 (2005).
 - [8] Kohn, W. & Sham, L. J. Self-consistent equations including exchange and correlation effects. *Phys. Rev.* **140**, A1133-A1138 (1965).
 - [9] Hohenberg, P. & Kohn, W. Inhomogeneous electron gas. *Phys. Rev.* **136**, B864-B871 (1964).
 - [10] Perdew, J. P. & Zunger, A. Self-interaction correction to density-functional approximations for many-electron systems. *Phys. Rev. B* **23**, 5048-5079 (1981).
 - [11] Giannozzi, P. et al. Quantum espresso: a modular and open-source software project for quantum simulations of materials. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **21**, 395502 (2009).
 - [12] Baroni, S., Giannozzi, P. & Testa, A. Green's-function approach to linear response in solids. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **58**, 1861 (1987).
 - [13] Baroni, S., de Gironcoli, S., Dal Corso, A. & Giannozzi, P. Phonons and related crystal properties from density-functional perturbation theory. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **73**, 515-562 (2001).
 - [14] de Gironcoli, S. Lattice dynamics of metals from density-functional perturbation theory. *Phys. Rev. B* **51**, 6773-6776 (1995).

- [15] Schrieffer, J. R., Scalapino, D. J. & Wilkins, J. W. Effective tunneling density of states in superconductors. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **10**, 336 (1963).
- [16] Soumyanarayanan, A. et al. Quantum phase transition from triangular to stripe charge order in NbSe₂. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **110**, 1623-1627 (2013).
- [17] Gye, G., Oh, E. & Yeom, H. W. Topological landscape of competing charge density waves in 2H-NbSe₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **122**, 016403 (2019).
- [18] Guster, B. et al. Coexistence of elastic modulations in the charge density wave state of 2H-NbSe₂. *Nano Lett.* **19**, 3027-3032 (2019).
- [19] Guillamon, I., Suderow, H., Guinea, F. & Vieira, S. Intrinsic atomic-scale modulations of the superconducting gap of 2H-NbSe₂. *Phys. Rev. B* **77**, 134505 (2008).